

ECOLOGICAL DESIGN IN THE CONTEXT OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY: PERSPECTIVES AND INNOVATIVE METHODS

Krivenko Olga ¹ [0000-0002-8949-0944] , Ru Changpu ² [0009-0004-9009-6938]

¹ Doctor of Engineering Sciences, Prof. of Department of Architectural Construction, Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture, Ukraine,

kryvenko.ov@knuba.edu.ua

² PhD student at the Department of Architectural Fundamentals and Architectural Design, Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture, Ukraine, 303512416@qq.com

Abstract. The article examines the evolution of ecological design as a component of the implementation of the circular economy. The authors analyze the transition from the linear production model to the circular economy, which contributes to the conservation of resources, the reduction of waste, and an increased efficiency in the use of materials. The article presents an analysis of the latest concepts in ecological design, including Emotionally Durable Design (EDD), Upcycling Design (UD), Trash Design (TD), Slow Fashion Design (SFD), and Zero Waste Design (ZWD). Based on this analysis, the authors determine how designers implement innovative approaches to creating products that combine aesthetics, functionality, and environmental friendliness with the principles of the circular economy.

Keywords: Ecological Design, Circular Economy, Innovative Design Trends.

Introduction. In the 20th century, the «industrial» revolution led to an increase in the destructive impact of humans on the ecosystem, which required an appropriate response at the level of preventing the consequences of the impact rather than overcoming them. This became the basis for the emergence of ecological design in the 20th century and its evolution in the 21st century, moving from merely satisfying consumer needs to finding innovative, sustainable and environmentally friendly solutions. In the context of "National and International in Design Practice", it is important to identify solutions that involve the integration of environmental principles into design at different levels - from local initiatives to global strategies that promote sustainable development and conservation of natural resources.

Literature review and main text. The Industrial Revolution introduced a linear

approach to business and production - "take, produce and dispose" — which was economically feasible because of the low prices of resources at the time (Den Hollander, 2017). The consequences of the linear model of business and production were an increase in the use of natural resources and environmental problems. The linear industrial approach was replaced by the circular approach, which aims to reduce waste and demand for primary resources in production (Stahel, 2010). The circular economy is a synthesis of several other theories: industrial ecology, blue economy, efficient economy, and biomimicry (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). Thus, the circular economy model can be characterized by the following principles:

1. Conservation and enhancement of natural resources;
2. Efficient use of resources — getting the most out of what already exists by making products and components in the system work longer.
3. Increasing the efficiency of the system - preventing the loss of value from the system and restoring it.

Product design that meets the principles of ecological design and the circular model of economy and production is based on a rational balance between functional, aesthetic and environmental components. This approach to design is actively developing, creating new concepts of modern ecological design. Let's analyze them in more detail.

- *Emotionally Durable Design (EDD)*, according to research (Chapman, 2005), is defined as an environmental design concept that seeks to create design objects that can evoke and maintain emotional attachment in users over time. Examples of EDD design solutions include: products made of natural materials that are characterized by durability; "household items with a story" that are passed down from generation to generation.
- *Upcycling Design (UD)*, according to (Pashkevych, 2019) is an eco-design concept that, unlike recycling, which transforms waste into its original forms or materials, involves the formation of new value and quality of design objects. Examples of UD reuse design solutions include: creating furniture from old wooden pallets or construction waste; products and objects made from recycled plastic; and the technique of patchwork for producing textile goods from fabric scraps.
- *Trash Design (TD)* according to (Emgin, 2012) is a design concept that uses waste and materials that are usually considered trash to create fashionable, stylish design objects. An example of TD design solutions are the installations of artist Vishulada Pantanowong, who uses trash to create strikingly detailed large-scale installations that raise awareness of plastic pollution on the peninsula, in Bangkok and around the world. Her goal is to spread the word about the importance of recycling and the circular economy.
- *Slow Fashion design (SFD)* can be defined, according to research (Fletcher, 2015), as a direction of designing items that have a long period of obsolescence and use, as they always remain fashionable, which reduces the negative impact on the environment. An example of SFD design solutions is a collection of decorative bio-panels presented by Wasoo as part of the Slow Hand Design Breath exhibition. The panels are made from locally produced natural waste (rice

straw, coffee husks, wood scraps). Each panel creates a unique feeling of warmth, and the natural fibers provide acoustic and thermal insulation, creating a healthy and safe indoor environment.

- *Zero Waste Design (ZWD)*, which according to research (Pinheiro, 2017) can be defined as a design concept that seeks to minimize waste and negative environmental impacts in the design, production, and use of products. An example of ZWD design solutions includes the creation of products that can be easily disassembled and recycled throughout their lifecycle. For example, the variability, upgradability, and adaptability of a product's modular structure allow for the avoidance of premature replacement.

Conclusion. Mounting human impact on ecosystems has driven the need for innovative ecological design solutions. These solutions embody the principles of the circular economy, aiming to minimize waste and resource consumption. Notably, the field of ecological design is experiencing a surge in effective trends (like Emotionally Durable Design and Upcycling Design) that bridge the gap between circularity and design practices, fostering a sustainable future on both national and international scales. Looking ahead, further research is crucial to explore the economic viability and scalability of these ecological design approaches. Continued research and interdisciplinary collaboration will be crucial in developing methodologies that effectively integrate these concepts. By leveraging technological advancements and fostering partnerships among designers, manufacturers, policymakers, and consumers, we can create resilient systems that prioritize sustainability.

References

1. Den Hollander, M. C., Bakker, C. A. & Hultink, E. J. (2017). Product Design in a Circular Economy: Development of a Typology of Key Concepts and Terms. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 21(3), 517–525.
2. Stahel, W. R. (2010). *The Performance Economy* (2nd ed.). Basingstoke: Macmillan Publishers Limited.
3. Geissdoerfer, M., Savaget, P., Bocken, N. M. P. & Hultink, E. J. (2017). The Circular Economy – A new sustainability paradigm?. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 143, 757–768.
4. Chapman, J. (2016, September). Design, emotion and longer-lasting products - Deliver specific insights to designers how to create emotionally durable products. *Conference paper: 10th International Conference on Design & Emotion*, Amsterdam. 74-79.
5. Pashkevych, K.L., Khurana, K., Kolosnichenko, O.V., Krotova, T.F., & Veklich, A.M. (2019). Modern directions of eco-design in the fashion industry. *Art and Design*, 4, 9–20. doi.org:10.30857/2617-0272.2019.4.1
6. Emgin, B. (2012). Trashion: The Return of the Disposed. *Design Issues* 28(1), 63-71.
7. Fletcher, K. (2015, April). Slow fashion: an invitation for systems change. *Fashion Practice*, 2(2), 259–265.
8. Pinheiro, E., Wachholz, L.A. (2017). Sustainable Fashion Strategies: A Study Applied To The Development of Clothing. *MIX Sustentável* 3(4), 157-172.